

Freedom of Speech and Expression – A myth

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Introduction

In a democratic setup, it is vital, and it is our fundamental right to express our satisfaction or dissatisfaction towards the working or the policies of the Government. The Indian Constitution provides the citizens, the fundamental right of Freedom of Speech under Article 19(1)(a) which guarantees that every person can express his opinions/ views on any issue, without being subjected to any fear, but it is restricted to certain reasonable restrictions.

The Human Rights Act, Article 10 defines the freedom of expression, which says that the individual has the right to express his view or opinion may be through television, radio, writings or pictures, or so on.¹

Changing Trend

But the recent trends explicitly made clear that the “Right to freedom of speech and expression” is in great danger. Anyone who criticizes the working or policies of the government is awarded sedition or is being charged under UAPA Act 1967. However, the main objective behind creating these laws was different.

But the way the government used these laws as a legal weapon to fire upon the criticizer, who raise their voice against injustice or arbitrarily working of the government is unfair. Several instances showed a clear picture that how the media

¹ <https://www.equalityhumanrights.com/en/human-rights-act/article-10-freedom-expression#:~:text=Article%2010%20of%20the%20Human%20Rights%20Act%3A%20Freedom%20of%20expression&text=Everyone%20has%20the%20right%20to,authority%20and%20regardless%20of%20frontiers.>

is also restricted, and they are unable to use their media freedom to deliver the proper and accurate information to the masses.

Freedom of Media in India

The position of India in the world press freedom Index 2021, speaks about the freedom of speech and expression given to the media and journalists in India. The report which was produced by the reporters without borders (RSF) ranked India at 142nd position out of 180 countries. India is being called the world's largest democracy and media is called the fourth pillar of democracy. If the position of media is so worse, then it is easily estimated that how sick the democracy is of that country. According to an article published in "The wire," it mentions "India is a dangerous country for Journalists"²

Trend of Sedition charge in India:

The offense of sedition is defined under section 124A, chapter VI of the Indian Penal Code, 1860. It is a cognizable offense, which means police can arrest the person who is charged with the offense of sedition without a warrant. There is no requirement for an arrest warrant. It is a nonbailable offence.³

According to the article published in "The Economic Times" it is stated that the number of cases registered under Section 124A (Sedition) has seen a significant and rapid rise, the number of cases filed increased up to 160 percent high. However, the conviction rate dropped sharply from 33.3 percent to just 3.3 percent in 2019, Source – National crime records bureau (NCRB).⁴

It is not wrong to coin that the law of sedition is often misused rather than used. Section 124A is often called modern TADA.

² <https://thewire.in/media/dangerous-country-for-journalists-india-ranks-142-on-world-press-freedom-index>

³ <https://devgan.in/ipc/section/124A/#:~:text=Whoever%20by%20words%2C%20either%20spoken,life%2C%20to%20which%20fine%20may>

⁴ <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/politics-and-nation/arrests-under-sedition-charges-rise-but-conviction-falls-to-3/articleshow/81028501.cms?from=mdr>

Conclusion

Freedom of speech and expression is the basic essence of democracy. It is imperative as a citizen to raise the voice against such malpractices by the government or any administrative body. Criticizing the work or policies does not amount to a threat to the national security or sovereignty of the Nation.